

Supporting Information

Large-scale individual tree species mapping using AVIRIS-NG and LiDAR data fusion

Appendix 1 - Spectral signatures from multispectral imagery. This plot presents the average reflectance profiles of the five dominant tree species, extracted from Sentinel-2 multispectral imagery (20-meters resolution). Reflectance values were obtained by sampling pixels corresponding to ground reference points. These profiles illustrate how spectral differences across bands (B01-B8A and B11, B12) can be used to distinguish between species, particularly between coniferous (*Abies alba* and *Picea abies*) and broadleaf (*Acer pseudoplatanus*, *Fraxinus excelsior*, *Fagus sylvatica*) trees. These signatures served as input features for the multispectral classification model.

Appendix 2 – Principal component analysis (PCA) of hyperspectral data. This table presents the results of PCA applied to AVIRIS-NG hyperspectral imagery, after removing bands that were not useful for classification (leaving 319 bands). It includes the standard deviation, proportion of variance explained, and cumulative variance for the first 13 principal components, which were retained for classification modeling. These components capture over 99% of the spectral variability in the dataset. This dimensionality reduction was necessary to mitigate redundancy among the spectral bands retained and to improve computational efficiency and model performance.

Component	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
Std. deviation	16.8408	4.4794	3.35490	1.55955	0.82809	0.52437	0.38118
Prop. of variance	0.8891	0.0629	0.03528	0.00762	0.00215	0.00086	0.00046
Cumulative prop.	0.8891	0.9520	0.98725	0.99488	0.99703	0.99789	0.99835
Component	8	9	10	11	12	13	
Std. deviation	0.32866	0.25670	0.19187	0.15479	0.13541	0.13029	
Prop. of variance	0.00034	0.00021	0.00012	0.00008	0.00006	0.00005	
Cumulative prop.	0.99868	0.99889	0.99901	0.99908	0.99914	0.99919	

Appendix 3 - LiDAR-derived features. This table provides a detailed list of 30 metrics extracted from normalized LiDAR point clouds using the 'lidR' package in R. Metrics are grouped into four categories: elevation, intensity, return number and shape. These metrics describe canopy structure and tree morphology, contributing to species differentiation. Selected features used in the classification model are highlighted in bold. Feature selection was based on correlation analysis, aiming to capture species-specific structural traits while minimizing collinearity.

Metric category	Description	Covariate name
Elevation	Maximum height	zmax
	Mean height	zmean
	Standard deviation of height distribution	zsd
	Skewness of height distribution	zskew
	Kurtosis of height distribution	zkurt
	Entropy of height distribution	zentropy
	Percentage of return above mean height	pzabovezmean
	Percentage of return above 2 meters	pzabove2
Intensity	x th quantile of height distribution	zq5 , zq25, zq50, zq75 zq95
	Sum of intensities for each return	itot
	Mean intensity	imean
	Standard deviation of intensity	isd
	Skewness of intensity distribution	iskew
	Kurtosis of intensity distribution	ikurt
Return Number	Percentage of intensity returned below th xth percentile of height	ipcumzq10 , ipcumzq50, ipcumzq90
Return Number	Percentage of first returns	p1th
Shape	Largest eigenvalue indicating the main direction of point cloud variation	eigen_largest
	Intermediate eigenvalue indicating secondary direction of point cloud variation	eigen_medium
	Smallest eigenvalue showing minimal variation direction in the point cloud	eigen_smallest
	Degree of direction variation	anisotropy
	Points alignment along a straight line	linearity
	How well points form a flat surface	planarity
	Proportion of horizontal variation relative to total variation	horizontality
	Describes how evenly points are distributed in all direction	sphericity
Local surface irregularity of bending	curvature	

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	Sum of intensities for each return	itot
Intensity	Mean intensity	imean
	Standard deviation of intensity	isd
	Skewness of intensity distribution	iskew
	Kurtosis of intensity distribution	ikurt
	Percentage of intensity returned below 1th percentile of height	ipcumzq10, ipcumzq50, ipcumzq90
	Percentage of first returns	p1th
Return Number	Percentage of first returns	p1th
Shape	Largest eigenvalue indicating the main direction of point cloud variation	eigen_largest
	Intermediate eigenvalue indicating secondary direction of point cloud variation	eigen_medium
	Smallest eigenvalue showing minimal variation direction in the point cloud	eigen_smallest
	Degree of direction variation	anisotropy
	Points alignment along a straight line	linearity
	How well points form a flat surface	planarity
	Proportion of horizontal variation relative to total variation	horizontality
	Describes how evenly points are distributed in all direction	sphericity
	Local surface irregularity of bending	curvature

Appendix 4 - Correlation matrix of LiDAR-derived features. This correlation matrix was used to identify and exclude highly correlated ($cor \geq 0.60$) LiDAR-derived variables. The size of the circles indicates the magnitude of the correlation, while the color indicates its direction (positive or negative). This step ensures that only independent and informative features are retained for modeling, improving robustness classification. This matrix was calculated using Pearson correlation coefficients on 1,000 randomly selected points from all raster layers derived from LiDAR.

Appendix 5 - Classification metrics for multispectral model, by-class and overall. Summary of per-class sensitivity, specificity, and balanced accuracy, along with global metrics (overall accuracy, Kappa coefficient and Area Under the Curve). While useful for broader vegetation mapping, this model showed lower accuracy compared to hyperspectral-based approaches, highlighting the limitations of multispectral data for species-level classification.

	Abies alba	Acer pseudoplatanus	Fraxinus excelsior	Fagus sylvatica	Picea abies	Std. deviation
Sensitivity	0.77	0.21	0.37	0.39	0.45	0.21
Specificity	0.89	0.93	0.87	0.85	0.74	0.07
Balanced accuracy	0.83	0.57	0.62	0.62	0.60	0.10
Global						
Overall accuracy	0.42					
Weighted F1-score	0.41					
Kappa	0.28					
AUC	0.64					

Appendix 6 – Classification metrics for hyperspectral + LiDAR model, by-class and overall. Summary of per-class sensitivity, specificity, and balanced accuracy, along with global metrics (overall accuracy, Kappa coefficient and Area Under the Curve). This model achieved the highest classification performance among all tested configurations. This configuration benefiting from the fusion of spectral and structural information, demonstrating improved sensitivity and specificity, particularly for *Abies alba*.

	Abies alba	Acer pseudoplatanus	Fraxinus excelsior	Fagus sylvatica	Picea abies	Std. deviation
Sensitivity	0.43	0.61	0.80	0.89	0.94	0.21
Specificity	1.00	0.95	0.95	0.93	0.87	0.05
Balanced accuracy	0.71	0.78	0.87	0.91	0.90	0.09
Global						
Overall accuracy	0.76					
Weighted F1-score	0.75					
Kappa	0.70					
AUC	0.76					

Appendix 7 - Classification metrics for LiDAR-only model, by-class and overall. Summary of per-class sensitivity, specificity, and balanced accuracy, along with global metrics (overall accuracy, Kappa coefficient and Area Under the Curve). Although LiDAR captures valuable canopy structure, this model performed the weakest, underscoring the importance of spectral data for accurate species identification.

	Abies alba	Acer pseudoplatanus	Fraxinus excelsior	Fagus sylvatica	Picea abies	Std. deviation
Sensitivity	0.25	0.44	0.16	0.36	0.55	0.15
Specificity	0.96	0.87	0.84	0.81	0.72	0.09
Balanced accuracy	0.61	0.65	0.50	0.58	0.63	0.06
Global						
Overall accuracy	0.37					
Weighted F1-score	0.36					
Kappa	0.20					
AUC	0.63					

Appendix 8 – Variable importance in hyperspectral + LiDAR model. Visualizes the contribution of each feature to the classification model’s performance. PC1 to PC13 represent principal components obtained after dimensionality reduction of AVIRIS-NG selected bands and are only spectral information. Other variables are LiDAR-derived features and characterizes canopy structure. Feature importance was computed using permutation-based importance, using function implemented in ‘caret’ package in R. Permutation importance measures the decrease in model accuracy when the values of a given feature are randomly shuffled, thereby assessing how much each feature contributes to predictive performance. This analysis helps identify which spectral and structural variables were most influential in distinguishing tree species, offering insights into feature selection and model interpretability. In our model, spectral features consistently ranked higher in importance than structural metrics.